

1 **An expression screen to identify genes important for trastuzumab resistance: Abcg2.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in patients sensitive or resistant to treatment with
7 trastuzumab for HER2+ breast cancer for discovery of genes that confer or support resistance to
8 HER2-targeted therapies in humans. In this manuscript we describe identification of Abcg2 as a candidate
9 gene product of the trastuzumab resistance gene expression signature.

10 Citations

11 1. Taylor, N.M., Manolaridis, I., Jackson, S.M., Kowal, J., Stahlberg, H. and Locher, K.P., 2017.
12 Structure of the human multidrug transporter ABCG2. Nature, 546(7659), pp.504-509.